

How to assess pododermatitis in breeding rabbits

Introduction

Pododermatitis (or sore hocks) is a chronic multifactorial skin disease that appears mainly on the plantar surface of the hind legs of rabbits. Some of the risk factors for pododermatitis are breed, age, body weight or claw length (Rommers and Meijerhof, 1996). For this reason, the disease mainly affects adult breeding rabbits, both females and males, being more frequent in heavy-weight rabbit breeds. Other risk factors are related to the rabbits' environment, such as high temperatures, humidity (Lebas et al., 198 in Rommers and Meijerhof, 1998), floor type (wire mesh flooring without either plastic mats or plastic platforms) and floor bedding (litter on either full floors or on plastic slatted floors) (EFSA, 2005; EFSA, 2020). The wounds may be colonized by *Staphylococcus aureus*, which can increase the severity of the lesion (EFSA, 2005). This progressive disease can cause chronic pain leading to poor welfare (Ruchti et al., 2019). Lesions with different severity can be observed, from simply a thickening of the skin (not necessarily painful) to bloody ulcers (likely to be very painful) on the plantar surface of the foot and more frequently on the hind pad (fig.1). This factsheet provides a description of two of the existing scoring methods used for assessing pododermatitis in breeding rabbits.

Legislation

Council Directive 98/58/EC of 20 July 1998 concerning the protection of animals kept for farming purposes.

“Any animal which appears to be ill or injured must be cared for appropriately without delay and, where an animal does not respond to such care, veterinary advice must be obtained as soon as possible. Where necessary sick or injured animals shall be isolated in suitable accommodation with, where appropriate, dry comfortable bedding.”

(Annex, point 4)

“Pending the adoption of specific provisions concerning mutilations in accordance with the procedure laid down in Article 5, and without prejudice to Directive 91/630/EEC, relevant national provisions shall apply in accordance with the general rules of the Treaty.”

(Annex, point 19)

Hiperkeratosis. Callus

Sore Hocks. Wound. Score Grade 1

Plantar Sore Hocks. Scabs

Medial Sore Hocks. Abscesses

Plantar Sore Hocks. Ulcers

Sore Hocks. Bloody Wound

Figure 1. Ulcerative pododermatitis in breeding rabbits (from Rosell and de la Fuente, 2013)

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Pododermatitis scoring method 1 - Classyfarm (2022)

The presence of pododermatitis and its **severity** is visually assessed on the plantar surface of both hind legs of at least **50 breeders with a point scoring scale (0-2)**. After the scoring, a final assessment (**Insufficient**, **Acceptable**, and **Optimal**) is to be assigned in relation to the percentage of animals with score 1 (more details are provided below).

Individual scoring system

Scoring scale	Description
Score 0	Absence of lesions and calluses in both hind legs or otherwise up to <5% of the foot surface area with hair loss.
Score 1	Presence of visible calluses with a hair loss >5% but without ulceration in at least one foot (fig.2).
Score 2	Presence of ulcerated calluses (sores) in at least one foot (fig.2).

Figure 2: Sore hocks scoring scheme (source Classyfarm). Score 1 (up) and 2 (bottom)

Final assessment

To assign the final assessment, one animal with a score 2 is considered equivalent to three animals with a score 1.

In this way, only the number (n) of animals with score 1 pododermatitis (pd1) is considered, to which the number of animals with score 2 pododermatitis (pd2) multiplied by three is added.

The calculation is as follows: $[(n \text{ pd2} * 3) + n \text{ pd1}]$

The result is then divided by the total number of animals observed (50) and converted to a percentage.

After the conversion is made, it is considered:

- **Insufficient:** score 1 in **more than 30%** of the animals
- **Acceptable:** score 1 between **20% and 30%** of the animals
- **Optimal:** score 1 in **less than 20%** of animals.

For example, if we observe **3** animals with **pd2** and **6** animals with **pd1** the final value is:

$$[(3 \text{ pd2} * 3) + 6 \text{ pd1}] = 9 + 6 = 15 / 50 * 100 = 30\% \text{ (Acceptable)}$$

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Pododermatitis scoring method 2 - Dalmau et al. (2020)

The **frequency** of animals with pododermatitis and its **severity** is visually assessed on both hind legs of **24 bucks** and **51 does** (when possible, 17 in the first week post-partum, 17 around insemination, and 17 post-weaning).

If the farm does not contain bucks, it is assessed in 75 does (when possible, 25 of each production stage).

Scoring System

Scoring scale	Description
Score 0	No evidence of hairless area or less than 2 cm
Score 1	Hairless area with callus formed (longer than 2 cm)
Score 2	Presence of an open lesion.

Final assessment

- **Non-acceptable:** more than **65%** with **score of 1** or more than **8%** with **score of 2**
- **Acceptable:** no more than **65%** with **score of 1** and **8%** with **score of 2**
- **Excellent:** no more than **50%** with **score of 1**, and **5%** with **score of 2**

Final considerations

The methods described use the terms "Insufficient," "Acceptable," and "Optimal/Excellent" as final judgments. These definitions can be interpreted as corresponding to "bad," "good" and "best" animal welfare.

Furthermore, these methods are mere examples, and different threshold values may be adopted based on new scientific findings, e.g. risk assessment or prevalence of disease in the area.

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